

MANAGEMENT OF SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN A MEDIUM-SIZED WHOLESALE AND RETAIL COMPANY: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the Supply Chain Management (SCM) of a medium-sized wholesale and retail company located in Itacoatiara, Amazonas, to enhance inventory management synchronization and reduce bottlenecks. The research aims to identify key performance areas and opportunities for improvement through the analysis of administrative reports, notes, and digital archives provided by the company's employees. Findings revealed inefficiencies in logistics operations, including inconsistent order processing times, manual inventory control prone to errors, and lack of advanced demand forecasting systems. Additionally, poor departmental integration and unoptimized transportation hubs contribute to high costs and delayed deliveries. The study suggests implementing a Warehouse Management System (WMS) to automate inventory control, adopting advanced data analysis tools for demand forecasting, and optimizing transportation routes. These improvements aim to increase operational efficiency, reduce bottlenecks, and enhance customer service, ultimately boosting the company's market competitiveness. The study also highlights the potential academic contribution of applying the SCOR model to Brazilian companies, offering practical insights into regional supply chain management.

KEYWORDS: Demand Forecasting; Inventory Management; Logistics Efficiency; SCM Automation; Transportation Optimization.

1. INTRODUCTION

The management of the company's Supply Chain Management (SCM) is tied to the processing of stock in and out. Knowing this, one might question the best way to control the product's logistical process. It is well known that SCM encompasses activities from retail to wholesale, covering everything from fulfilling requisitions to filling stock gaps, and is present in all departments of the company, both internal and external. Thus, it is evident that supply chain management is fundamental for the company to achieve economic development and full autonomy in differentiated management for its customers, aiming to achieve profitability and competitive advantage in the market.

In the wholesale and retail company, strict planning must be followed through stock indicators, where the established planning must be executed to meet market needs. This is widely related to orders, the transportation modes to be used, and strategic stock, combined among all these variables to meet the goals of the logistics control system (BALLOU, 2009).

Therefore, the objective is to determine the ways in which a company in the wholesale and retail sector in a municipality in the interior of Amazonas can achieve better synchronization in its stock management and mitigate bottlenecks.

2. OBJECTIVES

Analysis of the SCM of a retail and wholesale company in the city of Itacoatiara-AM, to provide better synchronization of stock management and reduce bottlenecks.

2.1. Specific Objectives

- Study a retail and wholesale company in the municipality of Itacoatiara-AM;
- Analyze the logistics activities of the studied company;
- Verify the SCM management of the chosen company;
- Propose improvements in the SCM of the company targeted in the case study.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study is exploratory in nature, aiming to describe the characteristics of the logistics system of a wholesale and retail company in terms of the efficiency of basic stock activities related to efficiently fulfilling orders. The goal is to identify the main errors in this system to improve the SCM of the studied company (RAUPP, 2006). The research is exploratory as it seeks to gather data on the efficiency of the SCM in the studied company, providing a better understanding of the sampled data for precise delineation of the researched data.

The primary documentation used for managerial analysis of the company's supply chain data comes from administrative sector reports, notes, and digital archives made available by company employees. This aims to simplify the research understanding process in a practical and straightforward manner.

The research is applied, as it aims to address waste in the processing of goods inflow and outflow for better supply chain management in the retail and wholesale sector, leading to sales losses, old stock, depreciation, and bottlenecks. It suggests solutions through supply chain diagnostics for problem identification and resolution (FERNANDES, 2016). It is qualitative because the research approach deals with collected samples, representing an understanding of the data to generalize the results obtained during the study. The primary focus is on studying better supply chain management in the company, moving from individual analyses to a conclusive generalization of the data, aiming for a more in-depth analysis of the data to generalize the finalized information (GÜNTHER, 2006).

The manipulation of these data regarding supply chain management involves information on stock control, processing, inflow and outflow, and the manipulation of these results for a more detailed understanding of the research presented. Thus, experimental research aims to determine how or why a phenomenon occurs. It involves control groups, random selection, and variable manipulation. This way, generalizations are sought through sampling techniques conducted during the experiment.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Results

4.1.1. Analysis of the Supply Chain Management (SCM) of the Studied Company

The analysis of the SCM of the retail and wholesale company located in Itacoatiara-AM revealed several key performance areas and opportunities for improvement. Based on data collected from administrative reports, notes, and digital archives made available by company employees, the following issues were observed.

4.1.2. Efficiency of Logistics Operations

- **Inbound and Outbound Goods:** The company exhibits inconsistencies in order processing times, resulting in delays and the accumulation of obsolete inventory.
- **Inventory Control:** Inventory management is manual and subject to human errors, causing inaccuracies in inventory levels and lost sales due to stockouts.

4. 1.3. Demand Planning and Synchronization

- **Demand Forecasting:** The company does not use advanced demand forecasting systems, relying on simple historical data that do not capture seasonal variations or market trends.
- **Departmental Synchronization:** The lack of integration between sales, purchasing, and logistics departments results in ineffective communication and coordination, affecting the ability to efficiently fulfill orders.

4.1.4. Identified Bottlenecks

- **Transportation and Logistics:** Transportation hubs are not optimized, leading to high transportation costs and longer delivery times.
- **Strategic Inventory:** The lack of strategic inventory planning leads to problems of overstocking or stockouts, negatively impacting operations and customer service.

4.2. DISCUSSION

4.2.1. Efficiency of Logistics Operations

The efficiency of logistics operations is crucial for effective supply chain management. In the studied company, the lack of automation and integrated inventory management systems is a critical issue. Implementing a Warehouse Management System (WMS) can help reduce errors and improve inventory accuracy. Additionally, automating the inbound and outbound goods processes can expedite order processing and reduce the accumulation of obsolete inventory.

4.2.2. Demand Planning and Synchronization

To improve demand forecasting, the company can adopt advanced data analysis systems and predictive algorithms that consider seasonal factors and market trends. Integrating information systems across sales, purchasing, and logistics departments is essential to enhance communication and coordination, ensuring that all departments work with accurate and updated data.

4.2.3. Identified Bottlenecks

The bottlenecks identified in transportation and logistics processes can be addressed by optimizing transportation routes and utilizing different transportation modes, such as maritime and road transport, as appropriate. The company should also review and adjust its strategic inventory to ensure products are available when and where needed, minimizing transportation and storage costs.

5. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the SCM of the retail and wholesale company in Itacoatiara-AM highlighted several critical areas that require improvements to increase operational efficiency and reduce bottlenecks.

The suggested improvement proposals, such as system automation and integration, the adoption of advanced demand forecasting tools, and transportation optimization, have the potential to significantly transform the company's operations, providing better customer service and increasing market competitiveness.

Implementing these improvements can also contribute to the academic consolidation of knowledge regarding the application of the SCOR model in Brazilian companies, offering a practical and regionally relevant perspective for the study of supply chain management.

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